

1 **Microbiome Data Management in Action Workshop: Atlanta, GA, USA, June 12-13, 2024**

2 Julia Kelliher^{1*}, Mashaal Aljumaah^{2,3}, Sarah R. Bordenstein^{4,5}, J. Rodney Brister⁶, Patrick Chain⁷,
3 Jose Pablo Dundore-Arias⁸, Joanne B. Emerson⁹, Vanessa Moreira C. Fernandes¹⁰, Roberto
4 Flores¹¹, Antonio Gonzalez¹², Zoe A. Hansen¹³, Eneida L. Hatcher⁶, Scott A. Jackson¹⁴, Christina
5 A. Kellogg¹⁵, Ramana Madupu¹⁶, Cassandra Maria Luz Miller¹⁷, Chloe Mirzayi¹⁸, Ahmed M.
6 Moustafa^{19,20,21}, Chris Mungall²², Aaron Oliver²³, Nonia Pariente²⁴, Jennifer Pett-Ridge^{25,26,27},
7 Sydne Record²⁸, Linta Reji²⁹, Anna-Louise Reysenbach³⁰, Virginia I. Rich³¹, Lorna Richardson³²,
8 Lynn M. Schriml³³, Reed S. Shabman³⁴, Matthew B. Sullivan³¹, Punithavathi Sundaramurthy³⁵,
9 Katherine M. Thibault³⁶, Luke R. Thompson^{37,38}, Scott Tighe³⁹, Ethell Vereen⁴⁰, Emiley A. Elo-
10 Fadrosh^{22*}

11

12 ¹New Mexico Consortium, Los Alamos, NM, USA

13 ²UNC Microbiome Core, Center for Gastrointestinal Biology and Disease (CGIBD), School of
14 Medicine, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC, USA

15 ³Department of Botany and Microbiology, College of Science, King Saud University, Riyadh,
16 Saudi Arabia

17 ⁴Departments of Biology & Entomology, Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA,
18 USA

19 ⁵One Health Microbiome Center, Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA, USA

20 ⁶National Center for Biotechnology Information, National Library of Medicine, National Institutes
21 of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA

22 ⁷Bioscience Division, Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM, USA

23 ⁸Department of Biology and Chemistry, California State University, Monterey Bay, Seaside,
24 California, USA

25 ⁹ Department of Plant Pathology, University of California Davis, Davis, CA, USA

26 ¹⁰Department of Biological Sciences, Florida Atlantic University, Boca Raton, FL, USA

27 ¹¹National Institute on Aging, National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA

28 ¹² Department of Pediatrics, University of California, San Diego, La Jolla, CA, USA

29 ¹³Department of Plant Pathology, University of Minnesota, Saint Paul, MN, USA

30 ¹⁴National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD, USA

31 ¹⁵U.S. Geological Survey, St. Petersburg Coastal and Marine Science Center, St. Petersburg, FL,
32 USA

33 ¹⁶Biological Systems Science Division, Department of Energy, Office of Biological &
34 Environmental Research, Germantown, MD, USA

35 ¹⁷Department of Biology, University of New Mexico, Albuquerque, NM, USA

36 ¹⁸CUNY Graduate School of Public Health and Health Policy, Institute for Implementation
37 Science in Public Health, New York, NY, USA

38 ¹⁹Division of Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition, Children's Hospital of Philadelphia,
39 Philadelphia, PA, USA

40 ²⁰Center for Microbial Medicine, Children's Hospital of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, PA, USA

41 ²¹Department of Pediatrics, Perelman School of Medicine, University of Pennsylvania,
42 Philadelphia, PA, USA

43 ²²Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Berkeley, CA, USA

44 ²³Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego, La Jolla, CA, USA

45 ²⁴Public Library of Science, San Francisco, California, USA and Cambridge, United Kingdom

46 ²⁵Physical and Life Sciences Directorate, Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, Livermore,
47 CA, USA
48 ²⁶Life & Environmental Sciences Department, University of California Merced, Merced, CA, USA
49 ²⁷Innovative Genomics Institute, University of California Berkeley, Berkeley, CA, USA
50 ²⁸Department of Wildlife, Fisheries, and Conservation Biology, University of Maine, Orono, ME,
51 USA
52 ²⁹Department of Geophysical Sciences, University of Chicago, Chicago, IL, USA
53 ³⁰Center for Life in Extreme Environments, Portland State University, Portland, OR, USA
54 ³¹Center of Microbiome Science, The Ohio State University, Columbus, OH, USA
55 ³²EMBL-European Bioinformatics Institute, Hinxton, UK
56 ³³Institute for Genome Sciences, University of Maryland School of Medicine, Baltimore, MD,
57 USA
58 ³⁴Office of Data Science and Emerging Technologies, National Institute of Allergy and Infectious
59 Diseases, National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA
60 ³⁵Benioff Center for Microbiome Medicine, University of California San Francisco, San Francisco,
61 CA, USA
62 ³⁶National Ecological Observatory Network, Battelle, Boulder, CO, USA
63 ³⁷Northern Gulf Institute, Mississippi State University, Starkville, MS, USA
64 ³⁸Ocean Chemistry and Ecosystems Division, Atlantic Oceanographic and Meteorological
65 Laboratory, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Miami, FL, USA
66 ³⁹Vermont Cancer Center, University of Vermont, Burlington, VT, USA
67 ⁴⁰Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics Division, Morehouse College, Atlanta, GA,
68 USA
69
70 *Corresponding author.

71 **Abstract**

72 Microbiome research is revolutionizing human and environmental health, but the value and reuse
73 of microbiome data are significantly hampered by the limited development and adoption of data
74 standards. While several ongoing efforts are aimed at improving microbiome data management,
75 significant gaps still remain in terms of defining and promoting adoption of consensus standards
76 for these datasets. The *Strengthening the Organization and Reporting of Microbiome Studies*
77 (STORMS) guidelines for human microbiome research have been endorsed and successfully
78 utilized by many research organizations, publishers, and funding agencies, and have been
79 recognized as a consensus community standard. No equivalent effort has occurred for
80 environmental, synthetic, and non-human host-associated microbiomes. To address this growing
81 need within the microbiome research community, we convened the *Microbiome Data*
82 *Management in Action* Workshop (June 12-13, 2024, in Atlanta, GA, USA), to bring together key
83 decision makers in microbiome science including researchers, publishers, funders, and data
84 repositories. The 50 attendees, representing the diverse and interdisciplinary nature of microbiome
85 research, discussed recent progress and challenges, and brainstormed actionable recommendations
86 and paths forward for coordinated environmental microbiome data management and the
87 modifications necessary for the STORMS guidelines to be applied to environmental, non-human
88 host, and synthetic microbiomes. The outcomes of this workshop will form the basis of a
89 formalized data management roadmap to be implemented across the field. These best practices

90 will drive scientific innovation now and in years to come as these data continue to be used not only
91 in targeted reanalyses but in large-scale models and machine learning efforts.

92 **Keywords**

93 Microbiome, environmental microbiome, standards, data management, data stewardship,
94 checklist, guidelines, workshop

96 **Introduction**

97 The field of microbiome research is rapidly growing with innovations spanning human, animal,
98 plant, and soil health, and implications for ecosystem resilience, nutrient cycling, food security,
99 and environmental responses to extreme conditions and climate change [1–3]. Institutions,
100 companies, and government agencies around the world have collectively invested billions of
101 dollars into understanding human microbiomes and their relationships to health and disease [4–6].
102 The importance of environmental, non-human host, built environment, and synthetic microbiomes
103 and their contributions to ecosystems is also broadly acknowledged within the research
104 community, but the investment, infrastructure, and public recognition have historically lagged
105 behind human-associated microbiomes [7]. However, this field is also experiencing a rapid rate of
106 growth as the sense of urgency for preserving environmental health in the face of a changing
107 climate becomes increasingly pertinent.

108 Researchers study microbiomes using techniques that interrogate their composition and function,
109 for example, by examining their associated DNA, RNA, proteins, and chemical signatures.
110 Combinations of these investigations, known as multi-omics, require the generation of large data
111 files that are difficult to produce, store, process, and share. These data are also produced by a range
112 of methods and instruments, such that data produced by different researchers or institutions may
113 not be directly cross-comparable or interoperable. The generation of microbiome data has vastly
114 outpaced the development of data management infrastructure and consensus reporting standards.
115 This disconnect hinders data reuse, including in meta-analyses and large-scale modeling efforts.
116 Despite efforts to improve microbiome data management [8–12], these data are often not
117 generated, stored, and shared according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and
118 Reusable) data principles that emphasize data reuse [13], which limits the growth of this field and
119 compounds existing research siloes.

120 In 2021, a group of human microbiome researchers collectively released the *Strengthening The*
121 *Organization and Reporting of Microbiome Studies* (STORMS, <https://www.stormsmicrobiome.org>) checklist which outlines reporting guidelines for human
122 microbiome research publications [14]. This consensus checklist has been rapidly and widely
123 adopted, and is already recognized as integral to promoting standardization across human
124 microbiome and epidemiological data and studies. Data management across non-human host-
125 associated microbiomes, the environmental sciences, and synthetic communities is in need of a
126 STORMS-like reporting framework. However, across these diverse domains, it is currently
127 challenging to consistently understand even basic study design or environmental parameters.
128 While the existing Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence (MIxS) standard [15] supports
129 sequence-specific metadata specifications including environmental ontologies, these do not
130 encompass the minimal requisite information about microbiome datasets (e.g., study and sampling
131

132 design, sample preparation or synthetic material construction, and other essential parameters to
133 enable cross-study comparison and data reuse). Significant gaps also remain in the adoption of
134 existing standards and their application across diverse environment types and also multi-omics
135 data [16].

136 The *Microbiome Data Management in Action* Workshop was convened from June 12-13, 2024, in
137 Atlanta, GA, USA. The workshop was funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF) and was
138 closely coordinated with the organizers of the subsequent *American Society for Microbiology*
139 *Microbe* conference. The workshop aimed to address the increasing need for a robust data
140 management ecosystem for microbiome research following the recommendation of the 2018
141 Interagency Strategic Plan for Microbiome Research [17] “to support the development of platform
142 technologies to enhance data access and sharing.” The workshop brought together researchers,
143 publishers, funders, and data repository representatives to identify local and national priorities.
144 The workshop sought to tackle the theme of data management broadly, with a more specific focus
145 on standardized reporting guidelines. The workshop attendees began generating a roadmap for
146 microbiome data standards across non-human host-associated microbiomes, the environmental
147 sciences, and synthetic communities leveraging the framework and lessons learned from the
148 STORMS reporting guidelines.

149 **Meeting Goals and Objectives**

150 The workshop goal was to ultimately advance microbiome science through coordinated data
151 management across researchers, funders, data repositories, and publishers. The workshop itself
152 was designed to be the first step in leveraging the STORMS reporting checklist to develop a
153 consensus roadmap to encompass non-human host-associated microbiomes, the environmental
154 sciences, and synthetic communities. The workshop was designed to lead to actionable insights
155 with concrete paths forward rather than open-ended discussions.

156 **Key questions**

158 The workshop aimed to address the following key questions:

- 159 1. Where are we now? What is the current ecosystem for microbiome multi-omics data
160 management, standards, and data re-use? What have we learned from past efforts?
- 161 2. What actions are needed from researchers, funders, data repositories, and publishers to
162 advance data management beyond current practices?
- 163 3. What developments, technical and otherwise, are required to achieve the standards, best
164 practices, community adoption, and data stewardship needed?

165 **Attendees**

166 To capture the interdisciplinary nature of microbiome research, the 50 attendees were selected to
167 represent diverse experiences and perspectives and with an understanding that participation of
168 groups typically underrepresented in science and engineering is critical to advancing microbiome
169 research. For example, the attendees ranged in their career stage (student to senior scientist),
170 science expertise (e.g., bioinformatics, ecology, multi-omics), studied environment (e.g., aquatic,
171 terrestrial, and animal-associated microbiomes), gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, background,
172 sector (e.g., government, academia), institution (included representatives from several Minority
173 Serving Institutions (MSIs)), and geographic location (included several international

174 representatives). Further, follow-on meetings and active recruitment and engagement with the
175 broader microbiome research community is planned to ensure community consensus in building a
176 collaborative data management roadmap.

177 **Meeting format & logistics**

178 The workshop was organized and run by a steering committee of five microbiome researchers
179 spanning academia, national laboratories, government agencies, and international consortia. The
180 workshop took place at the Georgia World Congress Center in Atlanta, Georgia, USA on June 12-
181 13, prior to the *American Society for Microbiology (ASM): Microbe* conference. The workshop
182 included a virtual participation option for invitees who could not attend in person. In-person
183 attendees were offered reimbursement for their travel expenses to increase inclusion and
184 participation. Name tags and pronoun stickers were provided to in-person attendees. Guidelines
185 for discussions and a code of conduct were provided to ensure respectful and safe participation.
186 Steering committee members monitored the virtual chat for questions, and a live notes document
187 captured participant notes, questions, links, and comments.

188 The workshop was divided into four main sections, described in detail below: 1) Welcome &
189 Workshop Overview; 2) Current State of Microbiome Data Management & A Path Towards Data
190 Stewardship Across Stakeholders; 3) Expert Panels; and 4) Breakout Sessions (**Figure 1**,
191 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13760811>).

192 **Welcome & Workshop Overview**

193 In the first presentation of the event, Principal Investigator Kelliher from the New Mexico
194 Consortium presented on the meeting objectives and deliverables, clarifying that the workshop
195 was intended to lead to outputs and actions (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13760905>). She
196 emphasized the interdisciplinary nature of microbiome research and why inclusion was prioritized
197 for this workshop. While the workshop was designed to be inclusive, it was also important to the
198 organizers that the power imbalances in the room be recognized, and the organizers offered
199 suggestions on how to mitigate the effects of these imbalances. The opening presentation set a
200 context of maintaining a positive, collaborative, non-judgmental environment, and emphasized
201 interest in hearing from everyone to facilitate open communication and effective collaboration.
202 This presentation also highlighted the follow-on ASM mini-conference session: *EEB-MC-001:*
203 *Microbial Data and Tools without Borders: Advancing an Open Science Ecosystem*, on June 13th,
204 which included a presentation to the ASM community on the workshop takeaways to obtain
205 preliminary feedback from the microbiome research community regarding these efforts. The
206 overview presentation ended with participant introductions of each attendee's name and affiliation.
207

208 **Current State of Microbiome Data Management**

209 Steering committee member and first author on the STORMS reporting guidelines publication Dr.
210 Mirzayi from CUNY Graduate School of Public Health and Health Policy presented on the process
211 of creating the STORMS guidelines, including timelines, lessons learned, and recommendations
212 for how to adapt these guidelines to non-human research. Questions from attendees during this
213 presentation led to discussions around five main topics: (1) the future of STORMS updates; (2)
214 how to engage the larger microbiome research community when gathering feedback; (3) how to
215 incorporate conflicting feedback into a consensus statement; (4) how to increase awareness and

216 adoption of standards; and (5) how guidelines can be effectively enforced by funding agencies or
217 publishers.

218

219 **Expert Panels**

220 This workshop convened four unique expert panels that allowed for targeted questions regarding
221 each group's roles in data management to be asked by the panel moderator and the audience of
222 participants. All panelist answers represented their personal views and did not necessarily
223 represent the views of their associated institutions.

224

225 ***Data Repository Representative Panel***

226 Five representatives from four data repositories and community resources - the European
227 Bioinformatics Institute (EBI), the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), the
228 National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON), and Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
229 (LBNL) - shared their experiences on how researchers currently deposit data into these
230 repositories, what metadata are required, and how the datasets are linked with other contextual
231 information or publications.

232 The panelists shared information about how well researchers are adhering to their repositories'
233 standards, and how these existing standards may need to change. The panelists also discussed what
234 they think next steps should be for data repository handling of data and how the repositories can
235 work with the other groups in attendance, especially publishers, to promote standardization and
236 proper data stewardship across the field of microbiome research.

237

238 ***Key Takeaways:***

- 239 ● Researchers feel like it can be extremely difficult, if not impossible, to properly deposit
240 their data into repositories without making mistakes
- 241 ● Researchers would like more trainings, user guides, videos, etc. to walk them through the
242 process of data deposition; this task often falls on students and postdocs
- 243 ● By the time researchers go to deposit their data, it is often too late to enforce standards,
244 especially for metadata, since they will have already collected their data
- 245 ● Data creators are often excited about making their data open and FAIR, but don't always
246 know how best to accomplish this
- 247 ● More obvious metrics for data reuse may be a good incentive; to enable metrics this
248 requires development of a robust culture of data citation
- 249 ● Data repositories generally do not have an abundance of personnel time and resources to
250 enforce standards or support community requests to use standards
- 251 ● Long-term sustainability is always a concern for every stakeholder group; it can be difficult
252 to know which repositories will be maintained long-term, and how the landscape will
253 change over time in terms of where people are depositing their multi-omics or other data
254 types

255 ***Funding Agency Representative Panel***

256 Five panelists represented four funding agencies: the National Science Foundation (NSF), the
257 Department of Energy (DOE), the National Institutes of Health (NIH), and the National Oceanic
258 and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA).

259 The panel included discussions on the funding agencies' current data management requirements
260 for researchers, and how these could change to adopt new guidelines in specific research fields.
261 The discussions also led to how interagency collaborations can be leveraged to generate more
262 broadly impactful data management guidelines and how data are and will be shared between
263 groups and agencies. Discussions about specific funding for data management plan (required
264 documentation by grant funding agencies) implementation and the potential for having designated
265 data managers as funded positions within grant proposals also occurred.

266
267 *Key Takeaways:*

- 268 ● It would be beneficial to have evaluation guidelines for proposal reviewers or agency staff
269 members, especially for when they are evaluating proposal data management plans or the
270 relevant text within a proposal outlining data management practices
- 271 ● Funding agencies have been providing more guidance for proposers writing data
272 management plans, but it is difficult, and not perceived as within the funders' purview to
273 provide detailed guidance across environment types, sample types, or other study-specific
274 aspects
- 275 ● Several funders have started enforcing more frequent reporting on the progress of the data
276 management plan throughout the project's lifecycle (e.g., in annual reports)
- 277 ● Some funding agencies are allowing researchers to request money specifically for data
278 management plan implementation
- 279 ● A uniform data management plan structure would be very difficult to implement across
280 funding agencies, but creation of something more modular and not too prescriptive may
281 work better
- 282 ● Having a minimum standard for a data management plan and making that broadly available
283 and achievable is key
- 284 ● Many funding agency data management policies are based on the needs, asks, and best
285 practices of the research community; however, this process cannot be solely 'bottom-up'
286 (from the research community), more guidance is needed from funding agency perspective
287 as well

288 *Publisher Panel*

289 This panel included four members representing *Springer Nature (Nature Microbiology)*, *Cell*
290 *Press/Elsevier*, *Springer Nature (BioMed Central)*, and *PLOS*.

291 This panel included discussions about how publishers can promote microbiome data management
292 best practices and how they can ensure compliance when researchers have submitted their
293 manuscripts for review and inclusion in their respective journals. The panel brought up that
294 journals cannot easily enforce standards, tools, or external checklists but can recommend options
295 for authors and reviewers. The panelists also discussed the interconnectedness with standards for
296 data repositories, as it is already established that many journals publishing microbiome research
297 mandate open access of the data in data repositories. Discussions also took place about data reuse
298 and what journals can do to ensure data is being properly cited and credited when reused in
299 publications.

300 *Key Takeaways:*

- 301 ● Journals want to make it as easy as possible for authors to submit; if a journal enforces too
302 much formatting or too many standards (e.g., a checklist), authors may choose to submit
303 elsewhere
- 304 ● Compliance checking is necessary, as without it author behaviors do not change. A lot of
305 compliance checking is still performed manually, and this requires personnel time and
306 money that not all journals have. For example, reviewers often don't go through the data
307 in excruciating detail (e.g., don't check all 500 accession numbers of data); artificial
308 intelligence is projected to help with this, but still in earliest stages
- 309 ● It has been difficult to get authors to abide by data availability rules; many authors submit
310 without their data being publicly available
- 311 ● Journals often want to see buy-in from the community first regarding a recommendation
312 or standard (e.g., STORMS) before adding it to their lists of recommendations, and even
313 more so to make a standard a requirement of publication
- 314 ● Researchers often think the journals hold more power in terms of enforcement of best
315 practices than they actually do.

316 *Researcher Panel*

317 The Researcher Panel consisted of four scientists representing a range of career stages, from
318 student to senior scientist, all from academic institutions across the United States. This panel
319 covered the responsibilities of researchers to adhere to data management best practices, and how
320 a standard set of guidelines can be created to be reasonably achievable, without excessive burden
321 on researcher's time and effort. Panelists were also tasked with suggesting advances they foresee
322 in their research if data management barriers are eliminated, and potential pitfalls if best practices
323 for data management are not generally followed.

324 *Key Takeaways:*

- 325 ● Machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) hold the potential to significantly
326 help researchers in many aspects of data management
- 327 ● Education about the importance of data management and metadata standards needs to start
328 earlier, as part of undergraduate or graduate coursework, or at least before a research
329 project starts; many researchers do not know what they should be doing until it is too late;
330 there is currently too much redundancy in researchers having the same issues throughout
331 the data management process
- 332 ● Researchers may also not be aware of current best practices; older methods may be
333 repeatedly passed down without improvement
- 334 ● There has been a culture change that needs to continue regarding how researchers view
335 FAIR data and data management; it was seen as a burden and necessary for publishing; it
336 needs to be continuously reiterated that this benefits the field now and in the future.
- 337 ● Collaboration across the field can be extremely helpful, but can be difficult with resource
338 imbalances across institutions; collaborations and sharing of best practices, standards, and
339 data should not be dependent on what another institution can offer you; inclusion of
340 historically black colleges and universities (HBCUs), minority serving institutions (MSIs),
341 and collaborations outside of typical networks can be beneficial for everyone involved; it
342 is important to develop standards that can work across a variety of groups and institutions
- 343 ● Standards need to be considered for every step of the data lifecycle including sample
344 collection, wet laboratory work, bioinformatics analyses, and data deposition

345 **Day 2: Breakout groups**

346 On the second day, workshop attendees were divided into six groups, with each containing six to
347 eight individuals. The virtual attendees formed one group of these groups. In-person attendees
348 were asked to sit with different people than the previous day and self-organize to evenly distribute
349 career stage and affiliation. The breakout groups were tasked with adapting the STORMS
350 guidelines to environmental, synthetic community, and non-human host-associated microbiome
351 studies. It was explained to participants that these recommendations will be collated, and the new
352 guidelines will be circulated throughout the microbiome research community for feedback before
353 a consensus statement is created. Once the reporting checklist is developed, it is envisioned to be
354 integrated into data management plan guidance, reviewer guidelines, an author checklist, and
355 overall guidelines for the field.

356 Attendees were also tasked with discussing how to increase community adoption, how to
357 communicate incentives, and how to educate others regarding standards and data management,
358 with an emphasis on tangible actions and outputs. The breakout groups also discussed what the
359 next steps for this group should be and how they would like to be involved moving forward. Each
360 group reported back to the larger group and kept their notes in a shared notes document so that all
361 groups could see the discussion items and outputs from other groups.

362

363 **Lessons learned**

364 The structure and logistics described here are intended to assist other groups in organizing a
365 workshop of similar size and scope. As has been noted throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, a
366 hybrid format for a workshop presents its own unique set of challenges. While it was ideal to be
367 able to offer virtual attendance for those who were unable to attend in person, having more cameras
368 and more microphones in the room would have made it easier for virtual participants to follow the
369 discussions and feel more included as a part of the larger group. Additionally, a more effective
370 audio-visual set-up for virtual attendees would have allowed us to invite more virtual participants
371 to the workshop.

372 The breakout groups were extremely effective for moving towards actionable insights rather than
373 discussions, which was a goal for this workshop. Additional time on the second day for these
374 breakout groups would have been preferable, as more questions could have been asked of the
375 groups. The engagement during these breakout groups was outstanding, and there were even some
376 breakout groups within breakout groups working on specific terms or a smaller subset of action
377 items. For the breakout groups, we found it beneficial to have attendees sit with other participants
378 they did not know very well, different people from the previous day, and according to the sector
379 they identify with (funding agency representative, researcher, publisher, etc.). This allowed for
380 productive conversations across various aspects of the microbiome research field, although it is
381 recognized that assigning a set of different tasks for each breakout would have minimized duplicate
382 work across the groups.

383 **Next steps**

384 A primary focus of this workshop was to start conversations with the intention of generating high-
385 impact outputs and sustained collaborations for the future. Immediately following the workshop,
386 the insights, outcomes, and the idea of a consensus roadmap was presented to the larger

387 microbiology research community as part of an open session *EEB-MC-001: Microbial Data and*
388 *Tools without Borders: Advancing an Open Science Ecosystem* at the ASM Microbe conference
389 as a means to gain additional diverse perspectives, keep researchers informed of standardization
390 efforts, and invite community feedback. There were approximately 150 attendees for this open
391 session.

392 Further, the workshop steering committee plans to recruit and engage with the broader research
393 community. Many of the workshop participants expressed eagerness to continue to meet regularly
394 as a working group to advance the reporting guidelines and data management best practices. The
395 proposed guidelines will be distributed throughout the microbiome research community to gather
396 ideas, feedback, and comments that will be implemented into the consensus checklist. This will
397 ensure that we are capturing the diverse needs of the community and generating standards that are
398 reasonably achievable. This workshop was also intended to be a launch point for a voluntary
399 interagency working group of attendees and any other interested parties that will meet virtually to
400 discuss the finalization of the guidelines, and discuss next steps and follow-on activities.

401 For scientific outputs, the workshop participants are working towards a consensus reporting
402 checklist for environmental, synthetic community, and non-human host microbiome data modified
403 from the STORMS checklist. This new reporting checklist, termed Standards for Technical
404 Reporting in Environmental and host-Associated Microbiome Studies (STREAMS,
405 <https://streamsmicrobiome.org>), will be broadly shared with the research community over the next
406 year to solicit feedback and build consensus. Application of these guidelines to data management
407 plan development, scientific manuscript submission, data submission to repositories, and
408 proposals and publications review, will be developed to help integrate the checklist into key
409 activities surrounding microbiome data streams.

410 Educational materials, outreach efforts, and strategies for lowering the barrier to adoption of
411 microbiome reporting standards will also be created, shared, and implemented, as existing
412 standards and guidelines in microbiology can be difficult to find, interpret, and adhere to. Several
413 workshop attendees indicated their interest in developing this educational and instructional
414 content, and a sub-group may be formed.

415

416 **Conclusions**

417 The *Microbiome Data Management in Action* Workshop assembled fifty participants across the
418 microbiome research field to begin creating a consensus set of guidelines for environmental,
419 synthetic community, and non-human host-associated microbiome data management and
420 reporting. The participants emphasized these goals require immediate action from every facet of
421 microbiome research, and everyone has a responsibility to do their part in improving microbiome
422 data management. The outputs from this workshop will assist in moving the field towards more
423 FAIR microbiome data across agency borders, working to make the microbiome research field
424 more equitable and inclusive. Data management best practices will benefit scientific innovation
425 now and in years to come, as these data continue to be used in large- scale models and machine
426 learning efforts. The outcomes of this workshop are intended to directly lead to an increased ability
427 to more consistently and comprehensively manage microbiome data to enable reuse, thus
428 unlocking research opportunities for all researchers, and improving the microbiome data
429 ecosystem. This will positively impact environmental, synthetic community, and non-human host-

430 associated microbiome research, which have demonstrated their importance to ecosystem health,
431 food security, and climate change.

432

433 **Data Availability Statement**

434 The workshop agenda (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13760811>) and introductory slides
435 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13760905>) have been made publicly available.

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443

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493 **Figure 1. Overview of the workshop.**